

Horizon Scanning Scenarios on Citizen Science Futures

IMPETUS Deliverable 4.5

Funded by
the European Union

Deliverable description

Deliverable	D4.5 Horizon Scanning Scenarios on Citizen Science Futures
Work Package	WP4 Policy with and for citizen science
Due Date	31st March 2024
Lead beneficiary of this deliverable	Public
Version	V3
Dissemination Level* PU / SEN	PU
Author(s) and Institution(s)	Alexandra Albert, Centre for Collective Intelligence Design, Nesta Aleksandra Berditchevskaia, Centre for Collective Intelligence Design, Nesta
Submission Date	27th March 2024
Reviewers	Antonella Passani, T6 Ecosystems Peter Baeck, Centre for Collective Intelligence Design, Nesta

*PU: Public / SEN: Sensitive, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Log of changes

To ensure the quality and correctness of this deliverable, we implied an internal review.

Version	Date	Status	Author	Action
V0	8th March 2024	Scenarios drafted	Alexandra Albert	Scenarios drafted
V1	14th March 2024	Scenarios revised	Alexandra Albert Aleksandra Berditchevskia	Redrafted following internal feedback
V2	20th March 2024	Scenarios revised	Alexandra Albert Aleksandra Berditchevskia	Redrafted following consortium feedback
V3	26th March 2024	Revised final draft	Alexandra Albert Aleksandra Berditchevskia	Revised and edited final draft

IMPETUS is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101058677. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Funded by the European Union

Table of contents

1 Introduction	5
2 Our approach	6
Figure 1: The different steps of our approach	8
Figure 2: Photos from the workshops	9
Table 1: Overview of participatory workshops	11
3 The Axes of Uncertainty	16
4 The Scenarios	18
Figure 3: The axes of uncertainty and the scenarios	18
4.1 Scenario 1	20
4.2 Scenario 2	21
4.3 Scenario 3	22
4.4 Scenario 4	23
4.5 How AI might impact citizen science	24
5 Next steps	27

1 Introduction

Through this deliverable and the associated Futures work, we sought to define desirable future scenarios for citizen science in the next 5-7 years. The aims of this are:

- to explore alternative ways that particular areas of citizen science to address the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and Green Deal might develop in the near future;
- to consider how key actors - citizens, government, business, NGOs and others - might behave under different conditions and circumstances;
- to identify the key requirements of policies that could support citizen science under different conditions.

This Futures work helps to contribute towards the overall improvement of the evidence base for making policy on citizen science, which is the main focus of our Work Package 4 on Policy with and for Citizen Science for the IMPETUS project. 'Futures' is an approach to identifying the long term issues and challenges shaping the future development of a policy area, in this case citizen science, and to exploring their implications for citizen science policy development. 'Futures' provides a set of research and modelling tools that policy makers can use to support the development of policy that is resilient to a range of possible outcomes.

2 Our approach

To develop our scenarios, we followed an adapted version of the different stages of futures methods described in The Futures Toolkit developed by the UK Government Office for Science¹. These are:

1. *Gathering intelligence about the future*

- We used Horizon Scanning to help us identify early signs of change in the policy and external environment that might be relevant to citizen science. This involved reviewing key pieces of domain-specific literature, as well as other academic literature, grey literature and blogs.
- This is typically a discrete step at the start of a Futures exploratory process. We took an iterative and continuous approach to horizon scanning to ensure that we explored signs of change throughout the scenario development process. This allowed us to account for relevant shifts in the policy landscape and to return to the trends most relevant to our scenarios as they developed (see Figure 1.).

2. *Exploring the dynamics of change*

- We used Driver Mapping to identify and map the change drivers – the key trends and factors shaping the long term development of citizen science. Identifying change drivers sits at the core of most futures and foresight work. Change drivers are typically characterised as the political, economic, societal, technological, Wider (global) context legislative or environmental factors (shortened to the acronym PESTLE).
- We then used this work to develop the Axes of Uncertainty to define the critical uncertainties for citizen science in the future and to frame the scenarios, by creating a meaningful and focused scenario matrix.

3. *Describing what the future might be like*

- We used scenarios to describe alternative ways that the external environment to citizen science might develop in the future, and to explore how different conditions might support or constrain the development of desirable citizen science futures. This

¹ <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a821fdee5274a2e8ab579ef/futures-toolkit-edition-1.pdf>

involved an adapted version of the Participatory Futures game², which was designed to inspire and provoke new, and sometimes unusual, ways to unlock public imagination about alternative futures. The Our Citizen Science Futures game (see image 2 of Figure 2) was then played at a series of different multi-stakeholder workshops to imagine different ways in which citizen science might develop within particular constraints around data and the institutionalisation or recognition and support for citizen science in the year 2030.

An overview of our approach is presented in Figure 1. below.

² <https://www.nesta.org.uk/feature/our-futures/>

Figure 1: The different steps of our approach

Figure 2: Photos from the workshops

Citizen Science Futures for Sustainability Workshop at Ars Electronica / Aleksandra Berditchevskaia (GB), Alexandra Albert (GB), Credit: tom mesic

Citizen science desirable futures - Game board

A

You are in a European capital city in 2030...

B

GATHERING NEW DATA, INFORMATION, IDEAS
What citizen science approach will help us tackle this challenge?

What is the specific issue we're addressing?

What data/information/ideas might help us?

How might we use this technology?

C

MOBILISING PEOPLE
Who might be able to help, and how can we best engage them?

What do we want people to do?

What might motivate them to be involved?

Who might be overlooked?

Participatory Citizen Science Futures game board, Credit: Centre for Collective Intelligence Design, Nesta

Citizen Science Futures for Sustainability Workshop Outputs at Ars Electronica Credit: Javier Pereda @TrinkerMedia

Through a series of multi-stakeholder workshops we sought to generate ideas for what citizen science might look like in these world views. We ran 7 workshops from September to December 2023 in a range of contexts, engaging 82 participants overall. See Table 1 for details.

Table 1: Overview of participatory workshops

Audience	Expertise of participants (+ total number)	Activities	Objectives
Ars Electronica	Digital Arts and Culture, Citizen	Participatory Citizen Science Futures	To identify plausible and desirable future

	<i>Science, General Public (18)</i>	<i>game.</i>	<i>citizen science initiatives addressing the SDGs.</i>
<i>Royal College of Art Global, Global Innovation Design MSc Students, London, UK</i>	<i>Global Innovation, Design, Arts, Academic Research (20)</i>	<i>Participatory Citizen Science Futures game.</i>	<i>To identify plausible and desirable future citizen science initiatives addressing the SDGs.</i>
<i>Connect, Collaborate, Create Conference, Paris, France</i>	<i>Citizen Science, Participatory Research, Academic Research (5)</i>	<i>Participatory Citizen Science Futures game.</i>	<i>To identify plausible and desirable future citizen science initiatives addressing the SDGs.</i>
<i>Portuguese Citizen Science Network, Coimbra, Portugal</i>	<i>Citizen Science (8)</i>	<i>Focused workshop to identify key trends that might impact the future of citizen science and to explore Axes of Uncertainty in more depth.</i>	<i>To identify plausible and desirable future citizen science initiatives addressing the SDGs and to identify key trends that may impact the future of citizen science.</i>
<i>Extreme Citizen Science Research Group, London, UK</i>	<i>Citizen Science, Technology, Academic Research (10)</i>	<i>Focused workshop to identify key trends that might impact the future of citizen science and to explore Axes of Uncertainty in more depth.</i>	<i>To identify technology and research and innovation trends that may impact citizen science futures and to research the drivers of the Axes of Uncertainty in more detail.</i>
<i>University College London, Environmental Conservation MSc Students, London, UK</i>	<i>Citizen Science, Environmental Conservation, Academic Research (9)</i>	<i>Participatory Citizen Science Futures game.</i>	<i>To identify plausible and desirable future citizen science initiatives addressing the SDGs.</i>
<i>Open Data Institute, Alan Turing Institute & Ada Lovelace Institute</i>	<i>Open data, AI, Data Science, Citizen Science (12)</i>	<i>Focused workshop to identify key trends that might impact the future of citizen science and</i>	<i>To identify data and technology trends that may impact citizen science</i>

		<i>to explore Axes of Uncertainty in more depth.</i>	<i>futures and to research the drivers of the Axes of Uncertainty in more detail.</i>
--	--	--	---

Why use futures methods for policy design?

Futures methods are a set of flexible and adaptable research and modelling tools that can be used to support the development of policy that is resilient to a range of possible outcomes. Flexibility makes Futures a powerful process that can be applied in a range of ways to help policy makers:

- deepen their understanding of the driving forces affecting future development of the policy or strategy area;
- identify gaps in their knowledge and suggest areas of new research required to understand driving forces better;
- build consensus amongst a range of stakeholders about the issues and how to tackle them;
- identify and make explicit some of the difficult policy choices and trade offs in the future;
- create a new strategy that is resilient because it is adaptable to changing external conditions; and
- mobilise stakeholders to action.

An example of an interesting application of Futures methods for policy design and innovation is in anticipatory regulation. Nesta has spearheaded the development of anticipatory policy and regulation which pioneers new ways of thinking about policy and regulatory infrastructures to support emerging innovation fields.³ Anticipatory regulation provides a set of behaviours and tools – essentially, a way of working – that is intended to help regulators and government identify, build and test solutions to emerging challenges. This approach to policy making is built around six fundamental principles to create policy environments that are inclusive and collaborative, future-facing, proactive, iterative, outcomes-based, and experimental. Our Futures work presented here for citizen science builds on these principles.

³ <https://www.nesta.org.uk/feature/innovation-methods/anticipatory-regulation/>

Perhaps most importantly, engaging more people in thinking about the future can lead to better decisions⁴ and can help to redress the imbalance in futures thinking being dominated by experts. This can help to unblock decision-making on complex challenges and ensure the benefits of emerging technologies are spread more widely. Engaging more citizens in shaping the future will lead to better policy-making, more effective socialisation of emerging technologies, and greater legitimacy for hard decisions, as well as creating the constituencies for long term change that can survive political and news cycles. Governments, city leaders, public institutions, funders, and civil society must be at the forefront of this approach, supporting it through funding, strategy and practice.⁵

Citizen science has been promoted as a potential method to help engage citizens in achieving sustainability targets and drive wider behavioural change across society. However, several challenges remain to the widespread adoption of the methodology and it remains underused. Some of these challenges might be overcome through better policy support and changes to the science-policy ecosystem. One of the reasons we think such work is important is that we acknowledge that the responsibility for making links to policy cannot be solely with citizen science initiatives themselves. It also needs to come from decision makers.

For this reason, our work on IMPETUS has focused on providing practical, step-by-step guidance for local-level decision makers on how to make use of citizen science data and how to localise SDG targets and indicators to local level. This work seeks to make the SDGs relevant to the local context and to raise awareness about how non-traditional data sources such as the data produced through citizen science can help with monitoring and making progress towards local sustainability targets. Its purpose is translating abstract targets to the issues that decision makers are responsible for at the local level - to make it much more relevant for local decision makers and to help shed light on the real value of citizen science for monitoring sustainability targets. In addition to developing these resources, this Futures work, including the subsequent backcasting workshops, aims to help foster dialogue between different stakeholders at different geographical levels across Europe, such as local decision makers at the municipal level, through National Statistical Offices at the national level and through the European decision makers at the international level.

⁴ <https://www.nesta.org.uk/report/our-futures-people-people/>

⁵ <https://www.nesta.org.uk/report/our-futures-people-people/>

This approach is aligned to previous policy engagement efforts by the citizen science community, specifically the EU Mutual Learning Exercise for citizen science that recommends a flexible, context-specific but also ambitious approach that builds on the substantial foundation for cross-national learning and inspiration. The main aim of the Mutual Learning Exercise was to identify and promote good practices, experience and lessons learned, in addition to policies and programmes for citizen science among 11 participating countries (Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Norway, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia and Sweden). The Mutual Learning Exercise aimed to achieve greater societal impact and increase trust in science through the leveraging of collective societal capabilities and insights, and to enlarge the scope and impact of Research and Innovation through increased societal relevance, responsiveness and transparency.

3 The Axes of Uncertainty

The four scenarios in this deliverable were developed based on world views determined by our Axes of Uncertainty:

- Institutionalised / Bottom-up citizen science;
- Open / Closed data.

We have used the Axes of Uncertainty to define critical uncertainties for citizen science in the future and to form the scenarios by creating a meaningful and focused scenario matrix. The critical uncertainties are the drivers that are important for citizen science, but which have an uncertain outcome. It is important to ensure that the matrix is meaningful for citizen science and that it defines the scenarios that tackle relevant issues and stretch thinking. The scenario matrix led to the development of four scenarios based on the following world views:

1. *Institutionalised Citizen Science / Open data:*

- Citizen science as an approach is well recognised and resourced by institutions across Europe. Citizen science initiatives in this worldview typically involve citizens collecting data for experts and citizen science has greater legitimacy and support from the broader scientific community and society. Developments related to the data produced through this form of citizen science mean that the data produced is held or stored less securely but there are more opportunities to reuse it and collaborate with different partners for better interoperability or combining of datasets together into larger systems.

2. *Institutionalised Citizen Science / Closed data:*

- Citizen science in this worldview is mainly led and funded by key institutions in power. Initiatives are well resourced with good access to funding. Citizen science initiatives are typically top-down, whereby citizens are mobilised through different approaches to contribute information and data for institutional experts to use for research and monitoring efforts. The data produced is held securely. Innovation resulting from it may happen behind closed doors, meaning there are less opportunities for collaboration.

3. *Bottom-up Citizen Science / Open data:*

- Citizen science is predominantly citizen-led and grassroots, meaning that citizens mobilise and collect data to address local and national concerns that are important to them. Resources are less prevalent but people make do with what they have. Grassroots citizen science initiatives typically unfold in do-it-ourselves fashion, potentially

challenging formally-sanctioned, expert-centric citizen science approaches. The data produced by citizen science in this worldview is held or stored less securely but there are more opportunities to reuse it and to collaborate with different partners to improve data interoperability to tackle complex social issues through combining datasets.

4. *Bottom-up Citizen Science / Closed data:*

- Citizen science is predominantly citizen-led and grassroots, meaning that citizens mobilise and collect data to address local issues that are important to them. Resources are less prevalent but people make do with what they have and make use of do-it-ourselves approaches. Such grassroots initiatives are typically anchored in local self-organised communities, and initiated by citizens instead of by formal institutions. The data produced is held securely. Innovation resulting from it may happen behind closed doors, meaning less opportunities for collaboration.

4 The Scenarios

The scenarios presented here are a mockup of the formatted versions that will be published on the IMPETUS and Nesta websites in April 2024. The aim is that the scenarios can be downloaded and used to stimulate discussion about the potential future of citizen science by anyone who finds them useful. The scenarios were developed via a synthesis of the horizon scanning work to gather intelligence about the future of citizen science, the exploration of the dynamics of change, which included the Axes of Uncertainty, and the outputs of the workshops to describe what the desirable futures of citizen science might look like.

In many ways, the scenarios themselves are less important than the conversations that take place around them. The purpose of developing them is to use future thinking to engage stakeholders and to develop a reasoned, robust perspective on possible future developments in citizen science. The scenario outputs presented here are designed to raise awareness of the issues shaping the future of citizen science and to stimulate debate about what is a desirable policy outcome for citizen science in the near future. How the respective scenarios map onto the worldview constraints of the Axes of Uncertainty is presented in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: The axes of uncertainty and the scenarios

4.1 Scenario 1

The Challenge

The increased negative impact of urban extreme heat - in particular indoor extreme heat - is pushing more and more cities to the point of crisis. Lowering heat stress in urban environments is crucial to protect the lives of vulnerable people, to ensure urban climate resilience for the future and improve quality of life for European citizens.

Intergenerational heat mapping for climate adaptation

A typical future Citizen Science Initiative

In the Netherlands, a university research centre for gerontology is leading a national citizen science project to gather large scale data on indoor extreme heat. The university and municipality-funded initiative has sponsorship from a technology company providing low cost indoor sensors. The initiative operates nationally, with international partners, benefitting from open citizen science projects that have helped improve data interoperability within and between countries.

The initiative's partners (public health departments and housing associations) set the research questions and priorities for data collection. Young people support older residents to install the sensors and this intergenerational approach helps to build strong social networks, tackling isolation and supporting the wellbeing of older residents. Young people learn research and analytical skills, and help to debunk misinformation by collecting data about local impacts and building trust in institutions. The data produced by the project is published in FAIR ways (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) and can be used for free, as well as combined with other datasets. Municipalities across the Netherlands are using the data to better understand which residential areas and communities are most at risk of extreme indoor heat, and to implement risk mitigation strategies accordingly.

Opportunity

By understanding how exactly heat patterns will evolve, urban planners can redesign cities to adapt to the impacts of climate change. Citizen science can help by gathering climate data and spatial heat patterns at the city-scale, supporting action through planning and individual or household behaviour change.

Risks & Limitations

Institutions have control over the level of granularity of the data that is made public and control how the data is visualised. Community groups struggle to get traction on the issues that matter to them. Their data cannot compare to institutionalised citizen science in terms of capturing data at scale, data quality and the aggregation of data from lots of smaller projects to be used interoperably with larger datasets. Bottom-up and small-scale citizen science more or less disappears, reducing the diversity of the broader citizen science ecosystem.

4.2 Scenario 2

The Challenge

Across Europe there is a waste disposal crisis. The European Commission has already introduced significant penalties and regulation to reduce consumption, and encourage circularity and recycling. An exacerbated cost of living crisis has taken hold of many countries across Europe, due to increasing inflation. The population more broadly has less capacity for volunteering, and participation levels in citizen science more generally are low.

Hyper personalised citizen science for more diverse participation

A typical future Citizen Science Initiative

Like many countries in Europe, Italy is experiencing a waste disposal crisis so private companies have started using citizen science to fill the gap.

There are several competing citizen science projects that pay people to monitor product packaging disposal. They also employ scientists and researchers to manage the projects. Citizen scientists are recruited to participate through market research agencies and paid via micropayment schemes for their work. Private companies use advanced marketing methods such as hyper-personalisation to compete for citizens to contribute data. They do this using real-time data to generate behavioural insights to create citizen science initiatives that are context-specific and highly relevant to individuals' needs.

The data produced by these initiatives are fed directly into companies' private data repositories on their waste disposal. Because data is privately owned, companies are able to shape the narratives on waste disposal and recycling. It is also possible to request tailored reports and specific analysis of the data for a fee. Publicly available reports on pre-defined topics/datasets are released annually. There is a well-functioning data ecosystem because companies maintain data infrastructure and supporting regulation ensures data interoperability.

Opportunity

The ease of participation and remuneration for citizen scientists can increase participation from minority groups and create a more diverse contributor pool. The competition between companies to attract participants has led to hyper-personalised offers that meet individuals' specific needs and interests. This has helped to build scientific literacy and skills across different groups and increased citizen engagement around waste reduction.

Risks & Limitations

Some companies end up not complying with data standards and protocols, using citizen science data for "greenwashing", by only publishing the data that is favourable to them, which means citizen science loses scientific integrity. Since citizen science data is held by private companies but not made easily available, and the data is not available to those who cannot pay for it.

4.3 Scenario 3

The Challenge

There is an ever-increasing gap between institutional discourse on climate adaptation and mitigation needs, and what's happening on the ground across Europe, meaning that there is a lack of impact on policy and decision making, and citizens' priorities are not aligned with policy agendas.

Collaborative citizen science for improved data quality

A typical future Citizen Science Initiative

An environmental NGO in Serbia has set up a citizen science initiative to track biodiversity loss in cities as a result of urban river pollution.

The initiative has been running for a few years and has established a network of volunteer professional scientists to cross check the data collection protocols and to validate the data generated by citizen scientists. Thanks to this ongoing collaboration, the initiative is starting to gain greater recognition at a national level by civil society and the media, and institutions such as the national statistics office and other traditional institutions are beginning to see the value of citizen science.

Geolocated data and multi-year datasets are produced through several long-running, self-funded citizen science initiatives. Because communities are involved in choosing the locations and focus of the research, the data produced is highly relevant to the citizens it affects and participation is high as people care about their communities.

Opportunity

This has led to greater recognition for citizen science which has become a way to join the dots between grassroots organisations and institutions and decision makers. For citizen science, there are opportunities for democratising access to data and information on pollution levels and for citizens to be involved in developing solutions to tackle climate adaptation issues, such as urban water pollution.

Risks & Limitations

A lack of institutional backing means that there is no support for the standardisation of datasets across and within initiatives. This means that citizen science data is less usable for national level monitoring. Bottom up citizen science is easier to do but to take action based on analysis of the data will still require a degree of institutionalisation, linking access to outcomes.

4.4 Scenario 4

The Challenge

Tackling the long-term effects of climate change and the heat island effect is now an urgent issue to adapt to and mitigate collectively. Crippling heat waves have been exacerbated by a surge in the cost of living crisis that has continued to rise over the last five years, leading to a lack of volunteering capacity for many individuals who struggle to find time to engage in non-work related activities.

Grassroots private data network for climate adaptation

A typical future Citizen Science Initiative

The Extreme Heat Climate Adaptation Initiative (EHCAI) was set up by a grassroots activist group in 2024 to mobilise those struggling from the impact of extreme heat in Barcelona, Spain. The EHCAI aims to empower citizens to become agents of change by raising awareness about urban extreme heat and providing tangible routes to action. Whilst resources and access to funding are limited due to the overall cost of living crisis, the organising group did a crowdfunding campaign and managed to purchase a large amount of heat sensors.

For some years, EHCAI has built up a network of volunteer members who generate evidence of the impact of hotspots, to campaign for adaptation measures for public space, and for building developments. This has led to the gathering of a municipality-wide rich dataset of sensitive, geolocated data on extreme hotspots over time across the city.

EHCAI set up a private data network to sell the data generated back to the municipality and other private companies, based on a community voting system. The community voting system allows those who are network members to decide who best to sell the data they collected to, and on what terms (prices, length of time, frequency of access etc).

Opportunity

Collective citizen data governance mechanisms create an opportunity for citizen science initiatives to generate revenue by selling access to citizen science data, and those involved in the initiatives can decide the best ways to dispense of this revenue.

Risks & Limitations

A lack of expertise and resources to ensure data interoperability creates challenges for citizen science initiatives, particularly around data security. A broader lack of investment in citizen science means a risk of community members resorting to less than legal or less ethical means of creating mechanisms to allow people who can't pay for the data to still be able to access it.

4.5 How AI might impact citizen science

In addition to the four scenarios described above, we started to explore the impact that recent developments in AI might have on the future practice of citizen science. The rapid progress over the last few years that has led to the creation of generative large-language-models and multi-modal generative models is likely to impact all sectors of society. At the same time, we have also seen transformative applications of traditional supervised machine learning approaches within citizen science, and this is also likely to continue. In this section, we describe how AI and citizen science might intersect in the future, and we also provide some examples of cutting edge practice.

Current cutting edge practice at the intersection of AI and citizen science

- Citizen science smartphone applications can include AI algorithms to recognise geographic locations where scientific data needs have not been met, incentivising participants to increase monitoring efforts at those locations through competition.⁶
- Acoustic loggers can be programmed to identify and record animal calls using classification algorithms such as AudioMoth.⁷
- Data labelling to generate large-scale training datasets to create models for science classification of images and sounds.^{8 9}
- Wildbook allows users to train AI algorithms to automatically identify species from images collected by citizen scientists.^{10 11}
- The Zooniverse Project Builder provides a free, user-friendly platform to set up online projects for citizen scientists to classify data that can be used to train AI algorithms.¹²
- Autonomous robots and unmanned aerial vehicles can be equipped with smart sensors to allow for wildlife surveillance in remote or

⁶ [Engaging citizen scientists in data collection for conservation](#)

⁷ <https://www.openacousticdevices.info/audiomoth>

⁸ [Identifying animal species in camera trap images using deep learning and citizen science](#)

⁹ [Bat detective—deep learning tools for bat acoustic signal detection](#)

¹⁰ [AI empowers conservation biology](#)

¹¹ [Wildbook: crowdsourcing, computer vision, and data science for conservation](#)

¹² <https://www.zooniverse.org/lab>

difficult to access places.¹³ Another example is the automated monitoring of ocean buoys that can collect data on algal blooms.¹⁴

- Using newer deep learning techniques, footage of animals can be rapidly and accurately processed after algorithms are trained to recognise species from labelled images.¹⁵ ¹⁶ This “supervised” deep learning requires manual image labelling,¹⁷ thus integration with citizen science can vastly accelerate processing time by harnessing large-scale citizen science communities to capture and label images used to train deep learning models.
- Where AI assists in understanding human cognition, metacognition and the nature of intelligence, such as the Creativity and Cognition Lab, at Aarhus University.¹⁸ To create hybrid intelligent systems, it is important to build new, powerful and innovative algorithms, but also to understand human skills and competencies more deeply.
- Firmamento is a multi-messenger astronomy tool for citizen and professional scientists. Although it was initially intended to support a citizen researcher project at New York University-Abu Dhabi (NYUAD), it has evolved to be a valuable tool for professional researchers due to its broad accessibility to classical and contemporary multi-frequency open data sets.¹⁹

Potential developments in AI citizen science integration

Some interesting potential developments in the integration of AI and citizen science include the following:

- Citizen-led cultural heritage / preservation projects are on the rise, funded by leasing qualitative data to companies developing and training Large Language Models (LLMs) on more diverse languages, values and customs. This is Inspired by the Aya project,²⁰ a global initiative led by Cohere For AI involving over 3,000 independent researchers across 119 countries. The result is a fully open-sourced dataset and model, pushing the boundaries of multilingual AI for 101

¹³ [Unmanned aerial vehicles \(UAVs\) and artificial intelligence revolutionising wildlife monitoring and conservation](#)

¹⁴ [Proactive management of estuarine algal blooms using an automated monitoring buoy coupled with an artificial neural network](#)

¹⁵ [A comparison of deep learning and citizen science techniques for counting wildlife in aerial survey images](#)

¹⁶ [Identifying animal species in camera trap images using deep learning and citizen science](#)

¹⁷ [Applications for deep learning in ecology](#)

¹⁸ <https://mgmt.au.dk/center-for-hybrid-intelligence/creativity-and-cognition-lab>

¹⁹ <https://arxiv.org/abs/2311.15102>

²⁰ <https://cohere.com/research/aya>

languages through open science. Another inspiring relevant project is Masakhane,²¹ a grassroots organisation to strengthen and enhance NLP research in African languages, for Africans, by Africans.

- “Personalised assistants” (LLM-based chatbots) help individual citizen scientists or citizen scientist groups to undertake more specialised and advanced domain-specific tasks so they no longer need institutional support.
- Institutional “AI Principal Investigators” help to coordinate massive scale citizen science projects, easing the administrative/coordination responsibilities of scientists and streamlining experience for participants.

²¹ <https://www.masakhane.io/>

5 Next steps

We will use the 4 scenarios and our exploration of AI trends as inputs into workshops with policy stakeholders. The focus of these workshops will be to identify suitable policy interventions and stimulate discussions about the future of citizen science. These workshops will take place over the next 12 months.

Drawing on the GOS Futures Toolkit methods for “*Developing and testing policy and strategy*”²², we will take a Backcasting approach to the design and delivery of these workshops. Backcasting is a method for determining the steps that need to be taken to deliver a preferred future. The aims of this approach are:

- to agree on a preferred future;
- to identify what needs to change between the present and the preferred future;
- to build a timeline that sets out the key changes; and
- to determine and address the key internal and external factors that might affect the timing or scale of change.

Typically Backcasting takes the form of workshop discussions that build on scenarios and involve people with responsibility for citizen science policy or strategy as participants. Participants don’t need to have developed the scenarios directly. Participants work backwards from the future and identify the key steps, events and decisions that will make it happen. One particular focus of Backcasting is to identify what lies within the control of the policy and strategy makers – and can therefore be delivered – and what lies outside their control and therefore needs to be managed. Backcasting is an effective way of connecting a given future to the present and identifying what needs to be done to deliver it.

As a result of these activities, we aim to produce a comprehensive set of policy recommendations and strategies that will help citizen science to flourish as a method that can support the achievement of sustainability targets. These policy recommendations will be published as Deliverable 4.6 towards the end of the IMPETUS project. An adapted version of the scenarios will be published on the Nesta²³ and IMPETUS websites²⁴ in April 2024, and will be available for download and use by anyone who finds them useful.

²² <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a821fdee5274a2e8ab579ef/futures-toolkit-edition-1.pdf>

²³ <https://www.nesta.org.uk/project/impetus-enhancing-the-impact-of-citizen-science/>

²⁴ <https://impetus4cs.eu/>